

The Future of Think Machines
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Note from 2022-May-15: I wrote this essay when I was in high school. Winner of the [Technology And Society Committee \(TASC\)](https://tasc-ca.org/) essay contest. <https://tasc-ca.org/>. This was written before I had knowingly used the internet (first in 1989) or a mobile/cell phone. We had an [HP Vector](#) 80286 DOS computer at home at the time. Before that, it had been an [IBM PCjr](#) and an [HP-150 touchscreen](#).

Neural networks present great possibilities in helping people to use their time more productively when the technology is applied wisely, but they also have the possibility to present us with another set of difficult moral problems to overcome. In the field of artificial intelligence, a new significant breakthrough is the modeling of biological neural networks on computer systems. These models are able to use some of the abilities inherent in a living brain to make decisions independent of a human operator. They are composed of a large number of small, weak processors that are interacting and linked together to form a neural system.

The new possibilities lie in such areas as vocal input systems for the handicapped, intelligent computer imaging, intelligent diagnosing computers, and intelligent, autonomous robots. These achievements are excellent as long as the serious, ethical problems are not ignored. This new technological advance in computer science will have a large impact on society.

There is a wide range of possibilities for positive applications of neural networks in unlimited aspects of life. In a household environment, this type of computer system can be used to monitor and protect the individual. A burglar alarm would not only be able to report a break-in, but would be able to make intelligent decisions on appropriate action. The alarm would be able to identify mistakes such as a cat in the house. Another household innovation would be an answering machine that would be able to interact with the caller to take better messages and pass information on.

There are many opportunities to improve employees' productivity with the use of neural networks. Voice entry devices would allow previously unemployable disabled people to work with computers and enter the workforce. Neural network computerized disease diagnosing programs will help provide doctors with a reliable and efficient way to determine a patient's problem.

With the invention of neural networks, robots will be able to "understand" the images they receive without the assistance of a human translator, and be able to act upon that information. These intelligent robots will be able to handle hazardous situations that people are currently put at risk for. Some situations such as toxic spills and nuclear power plant clean-ups are areas where these robots will be extremely helpful.

The above applications will be very valuable tools in the future, however, there are many ethical obstacles to be dealt with in the development of neural networking. With respect to military applications, we must consider to what extent neural networks be allowed so that the result is

not a sophisticated killing machine without scruples. In terms of the use of weapons, the final decision should always remain in the hands of people rather than in the circuitry of a machine.

We, as scientists, must make sure that the neural network products that are being created are complete and reliable before they are marketed and released to the public. Failure to do so could result in harm to the public in many ways such as mis-diagnosing an illness or the failure of a neural network system to report a serious flaw in a product.

Another minus of neural networks and of other new technologies is when people become too dependent on the new system, they often become inefficient or forget the previous technology. If the new technology were to fail, it might not be feasible to fall back on the prior methods. An analogy of this is the disaster of the space shuttle program. After a space shuttle exploded, the United States did not have a viable means of placing satellites into orbit. So while we may use new technologies and rely on them most of the time, like our use of pocket calculators, we must not forget how to add and subtract.

Putting too much control in the "hands" of computers is another concern. We must be responsible and stay in charge because there is a great temptation for the people in positions of authority to turn over decisions to computers. The human brain is still far above the most advanced and powerful machine.

Scientists' responsibility is to make technology available in situations where it is beneficial to mankind and to limit its effectiveness in harmful situations. Through educating people about neural networks, they will have a very significant impact on our future lives. As to all new ideas, there are positive and negative sides. Even though "there is no free lunch," neural networks will help improve many lives. The power of new technology can be used to advance mankind or pollute the earth.